

Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Refactorings for systems implemented in the Elixir functional language

Institution: DCC / ICEx / UFMG

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand the main refactoring strategies used in code implemented in the Elixir functional language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception about the refactoring strategies in Elixir (use frequency and impact on system quality)

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 20 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucasvegi@dcc.ufmg.br.

If you have questions about the ethical aspects of this research: Contact the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Minas Gerais (COEP-UFMG). Address: Av. Antônio Carlos, 6627. Administrative Unit II – 2nd floor - Room 2005. Pampulha Campus. Belo Horizonte – MG, Brazil. CEP: 31270-901. E-mail: coep@prpq.ufmg.br. Phone: +55 (31) 3409-4592. Opening hours: 09:00 AM to 11:00 AM; 02:00 PM to 04:00 PM (UTC-3).

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Próxima

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Limpar formulário

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

Select your country: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

Your city: *

Sua resposta

Voltar

Próxima

Página 2 de 4 [Limpar formulário](#)

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Survey on Refactoring for Elixir

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Perceptions on the Relevance and Prevalence of refactorings

Refactoring strategies are code transformations that do not alter a program's behavior. In our research, we aim to catalog and document refactorings for the Elixir programming language. We would like to know your perception regarding these refactorings.

Therefore, based on your experience, answer the questions below.

[Prevalence] How often do you perform this refactoring in your Elixir systems or see this refactoring being carried out in code implemented with this language?
(1 = it is very rare; 5 = it is very common)

[Relevance] How relevant is this refactoring in Elixir systems? (i.e., when answering consider the potential of this refactoring to have a positive impact on maintainability, comprehensibility, and evolution of Elixir code)
(1 = very low impact and relevance; 5 = high impact and relevance)

Notes:

- Each refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link containing code examples;
- You don't have to answer all questions items if you don't want to.

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Simplifying guard sequences]**.

This refactoring aims to simplify the guard clauses by eliminating redundancies but preserving the same behavior. For example, we can transform `(is_float(f) and f == 81.0)` into only `(f == 81.0)`. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Moving error-handling mechanisms to supervision trees]**.

This refactoring aims to remove error-handling mechanisms in a process (i.e., `try...rescue` statements) and adds this process to a supervision tree, thereby providing the non-defensive programming style (a.k.a. Let it crash style). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Transform a body-recursive function to a tail-recursive]**.

This refactoring aims to convert a *body-recursive* function into a *tail-recursive* one, thus improving runtime performance due to the *tail-call optimization* provided by BEAM. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Introduce Enum.map/2]**.

This refactoring restructures functions that use the divide-and-conquer pattern, making parallelization easier. To achieve this, it replaces a list expression in which each element is generated by calling the same function with a call to the higher-order function `Enum.map/2`. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Default value for an absent key in a Map]**.

This refactoring aims to replace the use of a `Map.has_key?/2` call together an "if...else" statement, with only a `Map.get/3` call. This transformation occurs when we expect a `Map` to have a certain key, and if not, we need to provide a default value. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Replace pipeline with a function]**.

This refactoring aims to replace a pipeline composed of Elixir's built-in higher-order functions (e.g., `Enum.map/2 |> Enum.into/2`) with a call to a function that composes it or by calling another built-in function with equivalent behavior (e.g., `Enum.into/3`). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Simplifying pattern matching with nested structs]**.

This refactoring transforms a pattern matching that performs a deep extraction in nested "structs" into a pattern matching only with the outermost "struct" in the nesting. After refactoring, accessing the value previously extracted is done by chaining strict access to the nested values. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Temporary variable elimination]**.

This refactoring aims to remove variables that are solely responsible for storing results to be returned by a function or intermediate values used during processing. Their usage is replaced with the values previously stored. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Transforming list appends and subtractions]**.

This refactoring aims to transform calls to the `Enum.concat/2` and `Enum.reject/2` functions into uses of the `Kernel.++/2` and `Kernel.--/2` operators, respectively. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Replacing recursion with a higher-level construct]**.

This refactoring aims to transform recursive functions into calls to Elixir's built-in higher-order functions (e.g., `Enum.reduce/3`, `Enum.map/2`, etc.). More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Defining a subset of a Map]**.

This refactoring aims to replace the manual creation of a `Map` subset, performed by accessing individually each of the desired key/value pairs from the original `Map`, with a call to `Map.take/2`. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Extract expressions]**.

This refactoring aims to extract unavoidably large and hard-to-understand expressions into smaller parts and assign them to local variables with meaningful names, thus facilitating the overall understanding of the code. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Typing parameters and return values]**.

This refactoring uses Elixir *typespecs* in a function definition to specify the types of its parameters and its return value type. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Remove processes]**.

This refactoring aims to remove unnecessary concurrent processes and replace them with Elixir regular *modules*. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition]**.

This refactoring aims to temporarily duplicate a definition when we want to test a modification in a code without losing its original definition. Once this new code version is approved, it will replace the [original one](#) and the duplication will be removed. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Reorder parameter]**.

This refactoring aims to reorder parameters of a function that are defined in an order that doesn't group similar semantic concepts. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

Assess the *prevalence* and *relevance* level of the refactoring **[Move file]**.

This refactoring aims to move a *project file* containing code such as *modules*, *macros*, *structs*, etc. to another directory, improving the organization of an Elixir project. More details and code examples here: [LINK](#)

	1	2	3	4	5
Prevalence	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

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Final remarks

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

Yes

No

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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